

Original article

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INTENSIFICATION TECHNIQUES IN HYBRID ACO FOR THE FAR FROM MOST STRING PROBLEM

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Abstract: *The Far From Most String Problem (FFMSP) is a hard combinatorial optimization problem encountered in sequence analysis, where the goal is to identify a string that is dissimilar to most strings in a given set. It has significant applications in bioinformatics, including mutation detection, pathogen strain differentiation, and in broader domains such as outlier detection, coding theory, and information security—where selecting sequences that maximize dissimilarity is essential. Solving the FFMSP efficiently requires advanced metaheuristic methods, as exact algorithms become impractical for real-world instance sizes. In this work, we conduct a systematic study on enhancing hybrid Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithms for the FFMSP by focusing on the intensification components. Specifically, we investigate and compare multiple implementations of the path relinking strategy, comparing random and greedy approaches for guiding solution recombination. In addition, we explore the impact of different local search implementations, analyzing both best-improvement and first-improvement neighborhood search variants. Comprehensive experiments on synthetic benchmark instances demonstrate how the choice of path relinking and local search configuration influences the solution quality and computational efficiency of the hybrid ACO framework.*

Keywords: *Mathematical optimization, ant colony optimization, FFSMP, local search, path relinking.*